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Artificial Intelligence and Patent Laws in India: An Analysis of Challenges before Law

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Abstract

The unauthorized use, reproduction and distribution of original and genuine products, along with the manufacturing which led to widespread, unregulated exploitation of intellectual property creation. Intellectual Property law protects those invention arising from human intellect, such as inventions, literary and artistic works, designs, and symbols. These rights aim to create balance the interests of creators granting them recognition related to their invention and economic benefit with the public interest in accessing innovative developments for the welfare of large public. However, rampant infringement of these rights undermines creators' legal entitlements, raising critical challenges for the state in enforcing Intellectual Property protections and ensuring the availability of adequate legal remedies. Within the broader spectrum of Intellectual Property rights such as patents, copyrights, trademarks, and geographical indications this paper focuses on the application of patent law to models and devices created through Artificial Intelligence. It explores the patentability of AI-generated inventions and the legal challenge over rightful ownership and patentability: whether such rights should vest in the human programmer of AI, the developer of AI, or potentially the AI system itself. It is also AI can also generate and create inventions independently meeting traditional patent criteria, it becomes essential to evaluate how existing patent laws apply and whether reforms are necessary regarding these unanswered question. This paper address the challenges, modernize patent legislation to address the rise of advanced, independent, and autonomous AI systems and technological advancement.

Keywords Artificial Intelligence and Patent Laws in India: An Analysis of Challenges Before Law.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is widely acknowledged to have originated in 1956 at a summer research workshop hosted by Dartmouth College. There, scholars examined the hypothesis that all facets of human learning and intelligence could, in theory "the conjecture that every aspect of learning or any other feature of intelligence can in principle be so precisely described that a machine can be made to simulate it". Almost 60 years later, question is raising into whether machines could acquire language, develop abstract reasoning, and engage in problem solving activity properly and previously this was done by human intellect and it has evolved into a successful technological field. By 2020, it was projected and predicted that AI would contribute approximately \$33 trillion annually to global economic growth and economy, outlining its economic significance in current position. This technological advancement related to AI, the emergence of AI has raised serious challenges regarding the applicability and efficiency of intellectual property protections and its related invention. In particular, patent law has emerged as the principal law and legal framework for safeguarding AI and its related innovations. However, the field of AI and its development and integration into society is contingent upon the capacity of intellectual property laws and legal framework to adequately comprehend and regulate its unique features and implications both societal and jurisprudential aspects. Various Legal scholars and Legal theorists have cautioned against early conclusions regarding the nature and scope of AI and its related invention, emphasizing the importance of current legal debates. By the virtue of this concern, the World Intellectual Property Organization[1] selected AI as

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the inaugural focus of its “WIPO Technology Trends” research series, focusing its critical and emerging role within the broader framework of intellectual property rights protection.

Objective of study

This paper address the challenges, modernize patent legislation to address the rise of advanced, independent, and autonomous AI systems and technological advancement.

Review of Literature

Historical Background of Patent Laws in India

The historical Background of patent laws in India has long history and it reflects the country's journey from colonial rule to a modern era, which is innovation driven economy. “The patent law in India came into existence in the colonial era. Before that, there was no accountable theft that happened regarding patents. The first legislation on the patents was Act IV of 1856 which was based on the British Patent Law of 1852. It granted certain exclusive privileges to inventors for a noted period of 14 years. But later in 1859, this Act was modified as act XV”[2]. during British rule, modelled after British law, to grant exclusive rights to inventors related to patent laws. Over the years, several amendments were made, culminating in the Indian Patents and Designs Act of 1911[3], which centralized the administration of patents laws. After independence in the year 1947, India recognized the need to reform its patent system to encourage local industry and innovation. This led to the enactment of the Patents Act, 1970[4], which limited product patents in critical sectors like pharmaceuticals to ensure affordable access to essential goods for the public welfare. However, with the advancement of the effect of globalization and India's commitment to the World Trade Organization's TRIPS Agreement[5] in 1995, significant amendments were made to align Indian patent law with international standards. Current laws are made to tackle the modern challenges related to patent and historical evolution of patent laws are divided into two phases mainly first one is pre-independence phase and second is post-independence phase.

Main Text

Pre-Independence Phase of Patent Laws in India

The evolution of patent law in India occurred during the British colonial era, it is incorporated primarily for the safeguard the commercial interests of British industrialists and to secure and promote technological advancement within the Empire. The legal framework that is the Act which was Act governing the grant of patents in India was originally modelled on the prevailing British patent statutes. Early patent regimes were designed to manage and regulate the monopolistic rights conferred to industrialist upon inventors and their assignees, ensuring that such exclusive privileges would serve as a catalyst for technological progress within the colonial territories and would increase the revenue for them.

The Patents and Designs Act, 1856[6] – The Patents and Designs Act of 1856 knows as the first formal patent legislation in India. Enacted with the primary objective of regulating, grant and protection of patents of British industrialist, the Act conferred/grants exclusive rights to inventors in return for the public disclosure of their inventions. This Act aimed to encourage innovation by balancing the interests of inventors with the broader goal of disseminating technological knowledge within the jurisdiction of British India.

Although the legislation was formally based on the British patent law, it lacked a comprehensive and contemporary approach, primarily serving to protect the interests of foreign inventors and enterprises operating within colonial territory of British India. The statute provided for the grant of patents over both inventions and designs; however, its substantive provisions were limited in scope, and the standards for patentability were neither rigorous nor clearly defined.

“Then in 1872, the act of 1859 was renamed The Patterns & Designs Protection Act and it provided more protection to the design, the act of 1852 continued to remain active for more than 30 years and meanwhile during this time no any big change took place in it but in the very year of 1883, there certain modifications in the patent law which were made in the United Kingdom took place and it was considered that those modifications should also be included in the Indian law, but all of these were amendments”[7]. As this act was not much clear related to patent invention as it was very limited in the scope.

Indian Patents and Designs Act of 1911[8] – “Comprehensive Framework: The Indian Patents and Designs Act of 1911 was a significant step towards modernizing patent law in India, replacing the 1856 Act. It incorporated more detailed provisions and was

influenced by the British Patents Act of 1907"[9]. The Act provided procedure of granting of patents in respect of inventions and designs that satisfied the triple test criteria of novelty, utility, and non-obviousness. While product patents were generally admissible under its provisions, specific exclusions were carved out most notably in relation to certain pharmaceutical substances for the public welfare. The legislation also incorporated mechanisms for pre-grant and post-grant opposition in case of fraudulent grant of patent, as well as procedures for the revocation of patents on prescribed legal grounds in the Act. And it has wide impact on India "The law continued to stand in India for nearly half a century and paved the base of the Indian patent structure. However, it is very much crafted in respect to the British interest rather than catering to the Indian developed sectors"[10]. In reality it only reflects the British Act in its objectives and it is enacted to protect the interest of British industrialist which reflects in the provisions as well.

The Post-Independence Era of Patent Laws – "Now in this act, the patent administration for the very first time came under the management of Controller of Patent and after Independence, it has come into account that the Indian Patents & Designs Act of 1911 is not continuing to perform its objectives as the political and economic condition of India was constantly changing there was a need for modernized patent laws and for this reason, there was the formation of a committee by the Government of India, under the Chairmanship of Justice Bakshi Tek Chand"[11]. This committee had the goals to review the patent law in India and also at the same time to ensure that the patent laws act as per the national interest. The interim report of this committee was submitted on the 4th of August, 1949 and there were certain recommendations in the report for the prevention of possible misuse of patent rights in India and this committee also suggested amending sections 22, 23, and 23A of the Patents & Designs Act, 1911 and this was also an observation of this committee that there should be a clear indication in the Patents Act to ensure

that the patents of necessary items should be given reasonable compensation"[12]. "This is so because necessities are to be achieved at a cheap and reasonable price by the public and the successful supply of which is the duty of the state and that supply can be secured by the procedure itself and the necessities might include the patents related to food, medicine, surgical apparatus, curative devices, etc. and therefore, it was advocated that the patentees of such a patent should be given reasonable compensation and after the recommendations are given by the Committee of Justice Bakshi, the Act of 1911, in 1950, as amended"[13].

The Patent Act 1970 - The Patents Act of 1970 marked as a landmark legislative reform in India's intellectual property era, signifying a departure from the colonial-era patent framework. The Patents Act of 1970 enacted with the objective of fostering and safeguarding indigenous innovation and promoting technological advancement, the Act sought to the balance between the rights of inventors and the broader imperatives of public welfare nothing overpower each other. Particular emphasis was placed on safeguarding public health and ensuring equitable access to essential medicines, especially within the pharmaceutical and healthcare sectors.

"In the meantime, there arose a question to revise the patent laws. The government was also keen to take the advice on such an issue of patents under intellectual property. Therefore, another committee was appointed in 1957 under the chairmanship of Justice N. Rajagopala Ayyangar for the abovesaid purpose and this committee submitted its report in September 1959"[14]. The report which was structured in two parts, with the first part was addressing the fundamental principles features of patent law. It critically examined the inherent drawbacks/shortcomings and negative implications of the existing patent law system, including issues such as monopolistic practices and barriers to access of the invention. This report offered a detailed analysis of these challenges and proposed a set of laws and policy recommendations aimed at rectifying systemic deficiencies and aligning the patent laws and policies with the latger public interest. "The second part gave an elaborated record on the clauses of the lapsed bill of 1953"[15]. "It was recommended by the committee that the Patent System should be controlled and maintained. The report by Ayyangar Committee recommended major changes in the law. This report paved the way for the Patents Bill, 1965 which was introduced in the Lok Sabha on 21 September 1965 but it fell off"[16]. "In 1967, the government introduced an amended bill which was sent to a Joint Parliamentary Committee"[17]. In accordance of the final recommendations of the committee, the **Patents Act, 1970** was enacted, which establishes a comprehensive legal framework for the protection of patent rights in India. Although this Act has undergone several significant amendments most notably through the **Patents (Amendment) Acts of 2002 and 2005** it remains a landmark legislation of Indian intellectual property law, which consistently safeguarding the rights of patentees and contributing to the nation's technological and industrial development significantly. "Then on 20 April 1972, the Patent Rules, 1972 were published and many provisions of the Patent Act 1970 were brought into force"[18]. The patent act of 1970 was enacted

with the objective of the public welfare with safeguarding the exclusive rights of the inventors which are as follows.

Promotion of Indigenous Innovation: To facilitate domestic research and development by ensuring that the patent system is accessible and beneficial to Indian inventors and innovators in every possible manner.

Safeguarding Public Interest: To prevent and protection the misuse of patent rights for the creation of monopoly that could restrict public access to essential and affordable goods, with particular emphasis on sectors of critical importance such as pharmaceuticals and agriculture exempt from patent right.

Emphasis on Process Patents: Reform introduced by the 1970's Act was the restriction of patentability in specific sectors most notably pharmaceuticals and agro-chemicals to process patents and make them accessible to public at large. This enabled Indian manufacturers to lawfully replicate patented products through alternative processes, significantly contributing to the expansion of India's generic pharmaceutical industry and enhancing public access to affordable medication.

Laws Related to Patent Right in India

The statutory framework related to patent right embodied in the Indian Patent Act, 1970, which is amended in 1999, 2002, 2005, and 2006, establishes the comprehensive legal framework governing patent protection within the jurisdiction of India. This Acts serves the two objectives of fostering technological innovation through exclusive proprietary rights while simultaneously establishing safeguards and protection the public interest against potential misuse of such exclusive right. These amendments were enacted to ensure compliance with India's international obligations under the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS), to which India is a signatory as a member state of the World Trade Organization, thereby harmonizing domestic patent law with globally recognized intellectual property standards is also the objectives of the act.

Chapter I[19] Preliminary provisions of the Act - The preliminary chapter of the Act in Section 1[20] establishes the definition clause, jurisdictional purview, and applicability. Section 2[21] is the definition clause which is the interpretative framework through which the entirety of the enactment shall be construed and read as, by providing statutory definitions of terminologies of substantial legal significance, including but not limited to "invention," "patentee," "inventive step," "novelty," and "new invention." these definitional provisions serve as the foundational legal parameters for determining the scope of patentable subject and what terms to be read as which is subject matter under the Act. The definition clause contained herein are of significant importance as they establish the substantive terms is to be read as against which patent applications shall be evaluated by the statutory authorities and tribunals in their adjudicatory functions. These provisions ensure jurisprudential uniformity in the application and enforcement of the patent regime contemplated under the Act.

Chapter II[22] Sections 3[23] and Section 4[24] of the Patents Act outlines specifically those inventions and subject matter expressly excluded from patent protection under patent Act and Section 3 enumerates categorical exclusions deemed non-patentable invention, including inter alia: inventions of a frivolous or fraudulent nature; inventions which opposes the public order or morality; mere discoveries of natural occurring substances are also not patentable; abstract scientific principles or theories; computer programs per se absent technical application are also non patentable; methods of agriculture or horticulture as prescribed also excluded from such category; and subject matter constituting traditional knowledge or aggregations/duplications thereof are also out of the ambit of patent act. Section 4 further describes patentability by expressly prohibiting the grant of patents for inventions related to atomic energy because it is matter of national security. These provisions collectively establish a statutory framework that balances the promotion and safeguard of innovation with the safeguarding of public interest, national security, and indigenous knowledge systems.

Chapter III[25] under Section 6[26] to Section 11[27] This chapter outlines the locus standi for patent application filing and vesting patent right in the true and first inventor of the invention, their legal representatives, or assignees thereof as the case maybe. It mandates submission of some specifications provisional or complete disclosure to enable persons skilled in the relevant art to effectuate the invention. Furthermore, the provisions establish a priority claim in simple words first come first serves mechanism whereby applicants may access earlier filing dates for similar applications, all this done to preserving novelty in competitive innovation of patent invention. These procedural safeguards incorporated ensures both legitimate entitlement to intellectual property

protection and adequate public disclosure to upheld public interest in furtherance of the patent system's fundamental objectives to grant the patent.

Chapter IV[28] – Publication and Examination of Applications Sections 11A to Section 21 - The chapter IV of the act defines mandatory publication of patent applications after expiration of eighteen months from the priority date, thereby disclosure objective inherent in patent jurisprudence. Examination proceedings, requires upon specific request by the applicant rather than suo moto initiation. During the examination, the patent office assesses evaluates the application that it follows the statutory criteria including novelty, inventive step, and industrial applicability or not. The provisions further establish the mechanisms for rectification of clerical errors and amendment of specifications, subject to prescribed limitations as the case may be, which enabling applicants which can be crucial for addressing any drawback or errors in the original disclosure before the invention is granted patent protection under the Act.

Chapter V – Opposition to Grant of Patent Section 25[29] to Section 28[30] - This chapter establishes the procedure of opposition of patent and pre grant opposition available to any person after publication and after grant opposition permissible within twelve months of patent issuance of patent. Such proceedings must be based upon statutory grounds which is mentioned under the act including anticipation, obviousness, or insufficient disclosure. This method of opposition functions as a critical safeguard against the improper grant of exclusive rights to patent inventions failing to satisfy patentability criteria, thereby preserving the integrity of the patent system is protected.

Chapter VI[31] – Anticipation Sections 29[32] to Section 34[33] - This chapter prescribes the statutory parameters for anticipation, thereby establishing the boundaries of novelty of the invention. It establishes circumstances

constituting disqualifying prior art, including pre filing publications and public use criteria. And also, it provides exemptions for disclosures at government recognized exhibitions and similar sanctioned venues, thereby preserving patentability notwithstanding such limited public exposure for the various security and others purposes. These provisions maintain a balanced approach to novelty assessment, safeguarding against public domain knowledge while protecting legitimate inventors from forfeiture of patent rights due to authorized preliminary disclosures as per laid down by the act.

Chapter VII[34] – Provisions for Secrecy of Certain Inventions Sections 35[35]to Section 42[35] - The chapter vests the authority in the Central Government to impose secrecy restrictions upon inventions which is of national defense or security interests. It empowers the Controller, in accordance of governmental directions, to issue secrecy orders related to disclosure of sensitive technological information. Such provisions establish a legal framework wherein proprietary rights of inventors are subordinated to upheld national security measures, thereby maintaining a balanced approach that recognizes both private intellectual property interests and overriding public security measures in relation to strategically significant innovations.

Chapter VIII[36] – Grant and Sealing of Patent and Rights Conferred Sections 43[37] to Section 53[38] - Upon satisfaction of statutory requirement as laid down in the Act and upon resolution of opposition proceedings, Section 43 of the act mandates the grant and sealing of patents. Section 48 of the act confers upon patentee's exclusive rights to prevent unauthorized making, using, selling, or importing of the patented invention within jurisdiction of India. Section 53 prescribes a patent term of twenty years from the filing date, which is contingent upon payment of prescribed maintenance fees. This statutory framework establishes the substantive boundaries of patent monopoly, thereby laying down the fundamental quid pro quo of patent law: limited exclusivity in exchange for innovation disclosure later may be used for public welfare.

Chapter IX[39] – Patents of Addition Sections 54[40] to Section 56[41] – In accordance to the provisions herein, in Act the supplementary protection in the form of patents of addition is hereby granted for modifications, improvements, or enhancements to inventions which are already subject to patent protection. Such patents of addition shall be in addition with the principal patent and shall not be subject to independent renewal fee obligations. These provision facilitates the protection of innovative addition of patent innovations without necessitating compliance with the exhaustive procedural requirements applicable to novel patent applications.

Chapter X[42] Amendment of Applications and Specifications Sections 57[43] to Section 59[44] - Notwithstanding prior submission, applicants may give another petition for the purpose of rectification or modification of patent applications and specifications of the patent. Such amendments shall be permissible for purposes of clarification or correction of unintentional errors which was previously there in the application; provided,

however, it is also mentioned that amendments shall not exceed the parameters of the original disclosure of the patent. All proposed alterations shall be subject to review and approval by the Controller, who shall ensure adherence to the principle that amendments remain within the scope of the initially submitted invention do not alter it completely, thereby preserving the integrity of the patent registry and excluding frivolous expansion of proprietary claims.

Chapter XI[45] – Restoration of Lapsed Patents Sections 60[47] to Section 63[48] - Where patent is lapsed due to non-payment of prescribed maintenance fees, this chapter establishes remedial procedures for reinstatement of patent after it lapsed, which is based upon reasonable cause for such default. Applications for restoration must be submitted within eighteen months from the date of expiration, accompanied by sufficient justification for such lapse. These provisions afford protection to patentees who would otherwise suffer irrevocable forfeiture of exclusive rights.

Chapter XII[49] Surrender and Revocation of Patents Sections 63[50] to Section 64[51] This chapter establishes procedural requirements governing both voluntary relinquishment and compulsory invalidation of right of patent. A patentee may, at their discretion, may surrender of patent rights when commercial viability or other considerations directs cessation of such protection. And also, revocation proceedings may be instituted upon grounds including, inter alia: fraudulent procurement of patent, obviousness, or insufficient disclosure of the claimed invention of

patent. Such revocation mechanisms serve to maintain the integrity of the patent registry by eliminating improperly granted rights.

Chapter XIII[52] Register of Patents Sections 67[53] to Section 72[54] - This chapter authorizes the maintenance of an official Register of Patents under the administration of the Patent Office to maintain such record, documenting ownership, assignments, encumbrances, licenses, and current status of the patent invention. The Register shall be accessible for public inspection, and certified copies therefrom shall be obtainable upon application. This is to ensure the transparency.

Chapter XIV[55] Patent Office and its Establishment Sections 73[56] to Section 76[57]-This chapter establishes the institutional establishment of patent administration, which includes the constitution of the Patent Office and appointment of the Controller General of Patents, examiners, and establishes other officers. The statutory powers, duties, functions, and jurisdictional of said officials are directed to facilitate expeditious processing, and administrative disposition of patent applications as soon as possible.

Chapter XV[58] Powers of the Controller Sections 77[59] to Section 81[60] - This chapter also vest upon the Controller quasi-judicial authority essential for the enforcement of provisions of the Patent Act. The Controller is hereby vested with powers to civil court. These adjudicatory powers are necessary for the resolution of disputes and preservation of procedural integrity throughout the patent examination and grant process.

Chapter XVI[61] Working of Patents, Compulsory Licenses and Revocation Sections 82[62] to Section 94[63] - This chapter outlines the regulatory mechanisms which governs utilization of patent and involuntary licensing within the territorial jurisdiction. Section 84 authorizes persons to petition for compulsory licenses upon demonstration that the patented invention: (i) remains not worked within the territory of India; (ii) is not available at reasonably affordable prices; or (iii) fails to satisfy public requirements. Section 92 further outlines for expedited issuance of licenses during periods of national emergency or in case of extreme public urgency. The chapter also prescribes grounds for patent revocation predicated upon non-working or contravention of public or defeat the objectives of the Act.

Chapter XVII[64] Use of Inventions for Government Purposes Sections 99[65] to Section 103[66] – In this chapter the government is authorized to utilize patented inventions for public purposes without patentee consent, subject to reasonable compensation. Such authority is vested in case of defense or public health. Jurisdiction over resulting in form of disputes is vested exclusively in the High Court of the state, thus balancing private proprietary rights with public welfare imperatives to fulfill the objective of the Act.

Chapter XVIII[67] Infringement Sections 104[68] to Section 114[69] – In this chapter Any unauthorized making, using, selling, or importing of a patented invention by a third party may constitutes infringement of the Patentee's exclusive rights. Upon establishment of infringement, the patentee may seek equitable relief in the form of injunction measures to prohibit further unauthorized activities. The patentee is further

entitled to get monetary remedies in form of compensation, including compensatory damages or disgorgement of profits derived from the infringing conduct.

Chapter XIX[70] Offenses and Penalties Sections 118[71] to Section 124[72] - This chapter outlines offenses including false patent representations, unauthorized patent status claims, and registry falsification as punishable by fines or imprisonment or both for anything which is prohibited under any provision of the Act, thereby deterring conduct that undermines patent system integrity and enforceability and safeguards of the right of patent holder.

Chapter XX[73] Miscellaneous Sections 125[74] to Section 162[75] - This chapter confers rule-making authority upon the Central Government, establishes delegation mechanisms for specified power.

AI Technologies and Patent Law

The term “artificial intelligence” was first time used, coined and introduced by John McCarthy in the year 1956, John McCarthy defined artificial intelligence as “The science and engineering of making intelligent machines”. As there is no official legal definition for the term “Artificial Intelligence” it is generally interpreted/defined as “the ability of machines to do things that people would say require intelligence”[76] “artificial intelligence (AI), the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings. The term is frequently applied to the project of developing systems endowed with the intellectual processes characteristic of humans, such as the ability to reason, discover meaning, generalize, or learn from past experience”[77]. The definition given by Britannica tries to interpret AI in effective way.

NASA interpreted and follows the definition of artificial intelligence under Section 238(g) [78] of the National Defense Authorization Act of 2019. which is as follows

“Any artificial system that performs tasks under varying and unpredictable circumstances without significant human oversight, or that can learn from experience and improve performance when exposed to data sets.”

“An artificial system developed in computer software, physical hardware, or other context that solves tasks requiring human-like perception, cognition, planning, learning, communication, or physical action.”

“An artificial system designed to think or act like a human, including cognitive architectures and neural networks.”

“A set of techniques, including machine learning that is designed to approximate a cognitive task.”

“An artificial system designed to act rationally, including an intelligent software agent or embodied robot that achieves goals using perception, planning, reasoning, learning, communicating, decision-making, and acting.”

artificial intelligence (AI) is the ability of a computer or program to match human behavior or thinking and perform human tasks. Instead of being programmed for every task, AI can find answers and solve problems on its own. AI employs methods and technologies such as machine learning, cognitive modeling, pattern recognition, and image and natural language processing. AI systems can be used to solve tasks that a human cannot oversee and solve due to their complexity. AI systems are versatile and accomplish different tasks. However, from a scientific point of view, the term AI is as fuzzy as the definition of human intelligence”[79]. This definition also try to interpret AI because it used yet not defined term. The three categories of AI systems identified by WIPO are – (i) “expert (or knowledge-base) systems”; (ii) “perception systems”; and (iii) “natural language systems”. [80] And according to Russ Pearlman, “the central goals of AI include reasoning, knowledge, planning, learning, natural language processing (e.g., understanding and speaking languages), perception, and the ability to move and manipulate objects”. [81] And essentials of AI can be termed as,

“Capable of predicting and adapting - AI uses algorithms that discover patterns from huge amounts of information”.

“Makes decisions on its own - AI is capable to augment human intelligence, deliver insights and improve productivity”.

“Continuous learning - AI uses algorithms to construct analytical models”. From those algorithms, AI technology will find out how to perform tasks through innumerable rounds of trial and error”.

“AI is forward-looking - AI is a tool that allows people to reconsider how we analyse data and integrate information, and then use these insights to make better decisions”.

“AI is capable of motion and perception”.[82]

“Computers can be trained with the use of these technologies to accomplish certain specific tasks including the generation of creative contents by processing huge data and recognizing certain specific patterns in the data so fed.”[83] AI means and includes various fields, such as machine learning, natural language processing, and robotics. It is future of technology in every possible aspect.

Legal Implications of Inclusion of AI and Patent Laws

“A patent is an exclusive right granted for an invention. Patents benefit inventors by providing them with legal protection of their inventions. However, patents also benefit the society by providing public access to technical information about these inventions, and thus accelerating innovation”[84] in simple word patent is an exclusive right of an inventor to protect its invention, Under Section 2(m) of The Patent Act 1970 the patent is defined as Patent means a patent for any invention granted under this Act, and Under Section 2(j) “invention” means a new product or process involving an inventive step and capable of industrial application in simple terms invention means any new product which is involving inventive step.

Under Section 2(p) “patentee” means the person for the time being entered on the register as the grantee or proprietor of the patent; by reading all these definitions it is to be said that if person involved in the inventive steps and developed any new product which eligible to register for patent under this act can be granted patent but this act is silent who will be the person who can register as patentee under this because under section 2(s) “person” includes the Government and the word include means it is not a complete definition and this started the debate whether invention made by AI which satisfy all the requirement under this shall be granted the patent under this act or refused to do so. “The patent application is filed by the inventor of the invention and it is important to decide the question relating to inventorship. Generally, an inventor is defined as a person who has significantly contributed to the conception of the invention and the term conception includes the idea creation, the approach made for the definiteness of invention, and the aspect of practical utility, there can be certain criteria to consider who cannot be considered as the inventor, firstly if a person has contributed by giving suggestions only, secondly if a person has acted on the instructions of the inventor, thirdly if a person's contribution is limited to consultation to perform experiments”[85].

The Challenges Posed by Artificial Intelligence in Patent Related Invention

“An automated intelligent system can be used to search and analyse the existing body of patent art to determine the patentability of an invention, one method of searching the patent database is to use keywords to find patents related to the Invention in question., often these simple keyword searches are insufficient because two patents addressing a similar issue may use different terminology”[86]. “Intelligent automated systems employing natural language processing or other AI techniques are able to analyse the content and context of patents in order to better understand the relationship between patents on a given subject, additionally, AI systems such as data mining tools or genetic algorithms can be used to analyse large portions of the patent database, or even the entire database, to find patterns or relationships between existing patents. this information could be useful in determining areas of high or low patentability, as well as the relationship between a technology and the social/economic effects of its patent protection”[87]. The Patent Office, from its establishment has employed technological instruments for facilitating the examination and issuance of patents. Initially patent application reviews were conducted with the assistance of the ‘Classification of American Patents’ a system originally conceived for the purpose of searching and analysing the existing corpus of patent literature. In the contemporary era, patent examiners are tasked with reviewing substantial volumes of intricate patent applications while operating under constraints of limited resources and toolsets. Currently, automated intelligence systems are under development to provide assistance to examiners in conducting searches, performing analyses, and ultimately comprehending the current state of the art in relevant technological domains. These automated intelligence systems represent not only robust instruments for providing support to human examiners in their official capacity, but

also potentially constitute powerful mechanisms capable of generating novel patentable inventions.

According to Section 6[88] of the Indian Patents Act 1970, the entitlement to apply for patent protection is vested in the person who qualifies as the "true and first inventor" of the invention. The definition given under the act provided in Section 2(1)(y)[89] establishes defines "true and first inventor" as "someone that does not include either the first importer of an invention into India or a person to whom an invention is first communicated from outside India." And also, the legislation remains silent on the positive criteria constituting 'inventor' or 'inventorship', thereby leaving these terms without explicit statutory definition leaves room for presumption. In the absence of such definition, the definition of inventorship is subject to interpretation on a case to case basis by the court according to established legal principles and judicial precedent. The determination of inventorship becomes a matter of legal necessity in circumstances involving more than one contributors to a patentable invention for instances where employer-employee relationships create potential questions regarding the attribution of inventive contributions because of these reasons determination is essential for proper adjudication of patent entitlements and the accompanying rights thereto. In the case of V.B. Mohammed Ibrahim v. Alfred Schafrnek[90], Hon'ble court held that "since the plaintiff has not contributed any part of his ingenuity or skill or technical knowledge towards the invention and only for the act of financial contribution for running the experiments, the plaintiff could not be considered as the inventor." Hon'ble court further observed that "neither a corporation nor a financial partner can be the sole inventor and only the natural person who contributes their skill and knowledge to the innovation can legally claim the inventorship."

For those unfamiliar with the laws and legal framework, the Indian Patent Office's position on the patentability of Computer-Related Inventions (CRIs) in current scenario AI invention lacks the clarity. The Indian CRI guidelines have been the subject of considerable debate in recent years, and the Patent Office has responded to these debates by making significant and sometimes abrupt revisions to its issued guidelines, there are three main issues posed by AI in patent laws, firstly whether AI as an invention is eligible subject matter, secondly who is the true and first inventor and Thirdly who owns liability for, the acts of the AI technology which is remain unanswered.

1. Whether Inventions by AI are Eligible Subject Matter Related to Patent

There current ongoing and persistent debate as to whether the grant of patent rights over Computer-Related Inventions (CRIs) that is AI serves to stimulate investment in software-related research and, by extension, promotes innovation. A balanced, approach appears to be the most and sensible course of action, and it is incumbent upon the Indian Patent Office to address this matter urgently. This should be discussed with every possible share holder of invention and authority to make a comprehensive and prudent legal mechanism and framework in India. "The EPO has already held its first conference on AI and patenting; if India wants to be one of the leaders in AI, it must adapt its patent regime to ensure that the country remains an opportunity for innovators and the government must ensure that AI's impact on patents is dealt with systematically and to the benefit of the technology community, especially if India is to become a creator of AI, and not a mere adopter"[91]. The European Patent Office (EPO) has already conducted its inaugural conference addressing the challenge posed by artificial intelligence (AI) on patenting. If India aspires itself as a global leader in the field of AI, it is legal framework related all aspect of AI must be adapted to maintain the country's attractiveness as a jurisdiction for innovation.

2. Who is the True and First Inventor

There is no legal ambiguity under current Indian patent law regarding the determination of inventorship whether it made by Human Intervention; in such scenarios, the human individual responsible for the conception or material contribution to the invention which is the deemed the inventor. However, a more complex and unresolved legal question emerges when considering whether artificial intelligence which created the patentable subject matter themselves can or should be recognized as 'inventors' in circumstances where the AI independently generates patentable inventions without human input or direction or command. Under Section 6[92] of the Patents Act, 1970, an application for a patent may be made by the 'true and first inventor' The statutory language presumption that the inventor is a natural person, as reinforced by Section 2(y), which defines "person" in which recognised government which means legal person can also be granted patent. Consequently, the Act does not deny non-human inventors, such as AI systems, as having eligibility to apply for inventorship. This raises significant legal challenges, particularly related to development of independent AI systems capable of producing novel, non-obvious, and industrially applicable outputs that, as it is produced by a human, would qualify as patentable inventions.

The current statutory and legal framework lacks provisions addressing whether AI-generated inventions should be handled and granted within the patent system, creating uncertainty for innovators, developers, and legal practitioners. If India seeks to remain at the updated of technology and to provide legal certainty in this field of patent, it may become necessary for lawmakers and policymakers to amend the Patents Act to clarify the treatment of AI-generated inventions. This would involve careful consideration of questions related to ownership, rights allocation, public disclosure, and the broader

implications for innovation policy, ensuring that the patent system remains both fair and updated in the case of technological change.

“Section 2(1)(p)10, is the ‘person’ entered on the patent office register as the grantee or owner of the patent. Intuitively, this suggests that an inventor and person must mean a natural person and however, Section 2(1)(s)11 defines ‘person’ to include the government, a non-natural entity moreover, ‘true and first inventor’ has an exclusionary definition and there is no mention of a natural person (Section 2(1)(y12))”[93]. “Thus, the Patents Act arguably does not require a particular threshold of human control or input in the invention process for granting patent rights per se, and frames the questions of inventiveness in terms of creation (i.e., ‘new product or process’ or ‘technical advance as compared to the existing knowledge’, in Sections 2(1)(j)(ja)13) and while these provisions do not expressly impose the requirement for an inventor to be a natural person, the predisposition appears to require human intervention for an invention to be considered patentable”[94].

3. Who Owns Liability for, The Acts of the AI Technology

Section 48 of the Patents Act grants the patentee the exclusive right to restrain unauthorized third parties from engaging in specified acts with respect to the patented invention. A critical legal issue arises as to whether an artificial intelligence (AI) system possesses the capacity to give the consent. If AI is deemed capable to give consent, the question then arises: by what way would a party obtain valid consent from the AI. This extends to concern related to ownership, particularly in relation to assignment or acquisition of patent rights. Where an invention is transferred to a legal entity such as a corporation entitled to enforce the patent, an issue of legal significance is whether an AI is competent to effectuate such a transfer or assignment of ownership.

Following a finding of patent infringement, the infringing party is typically liable to pay compensatory damages to the patent holder these may take the form of lost royalties. In certain cases, injunctive relief may also be granted to restrain further infringing conduct. However, challenges arise where the infringing activity is acted by an AI system. This raises the question: How would judicial remedies be enforced against an AI? Further, legal accountability must be addressed: in those cases, where infringing conduct or any unlawful act originates from an AI, is liability attributed to the AI itself, its developer, its owner, or its operator? The law is silent and unclear in these scenarios, in circumstances where the unlawful act cannot be directly attributed to a natural person, who then bears legal responsibility? These concerns and challenges have become ongoing legal discussion because of surrounding the uncertainties associated with artificial intelligence, which is extending beyond the domain of intellectual property into broader considerations of criminal and civil liability. renowned, legal scholar Gabriel Hallevy has explained three theoretical frameworks of criminal liability that provide valuable insight into the attribution of legal responsibility to AI systems and the challenges inherent in such determinations. Which are as follows Firstly, “The first is the ‘perpetration-via-another’ liability model, wherein mens rea is not attributable to an AI entity and the perpetrator would be either the programmer of the AI software or perhaps the end user”[95], Secondly, the ‘natural-probable-consequence’ liability model assumes deep involvement of the programmers or users in the AI entity’s daily activity, but without intent to commit an offence. However, since ignorance of law is not a defence, this assumes that the programmers or users of an AI should have known about the probability of the commission of the specific offence, and hence holds them to be liable”[96], Thirdly, “the ‘direct liability’ model focuses on the AI entity itself, and suggests that the AI entity would be liable as if it were a human”[97].

Measure can be taken to Address these Futuristic Challenges

India is facing issue related challenges posed by AI on patent laws, but US court addresses these challenges very efficiently and in various pronouncement discussed these issues. In the case of *Thaler v. Vidal*[98], the court affirmed that “only a natural person can be an inventor of the invention and such inventorship cannot be granted to AI in cases where the invention is made with the assistance of AI”. The contention that artificial intelligence may be eligible to be granted patent rights justified by the reasoning given by the United States Supreme Court in the case of *Goldstein v. California*[99], wherein the Court’s observations may be interpreted as “authors and inventors should not be interpreted in a narrow literal sense, but in a broad scope to reflect constitutional principles”[100], this opened up the scope for the patent right may be granted to AI where there is no human intervention. “Though it is an accepted view that generally data is enabled into the AI system by human interference, this task does not give the human the sole authority to be considered as the inventor of the patent invention and the primary condition for the principle of inventorship is making a significant contribution toward the invention”[101]. The recognition and protection of patents involving artificial intelligence is to protect technological innovation. “It is considered that there must be a permanent idea of the invention, which is sufficient for the skilled person to perform or carry out the invention without experimentation”[102]. And later on “The issue arises regarding which entity will reap economic benefits from the innovation, where the patent is granted to AI and it is considered that when an AI is granted patent ownership, a dispute relating to the ownership of the patent will arise and the best possible method is where the Patent Office, licenses or assigns the patent that is AI-generated to AI users, which includes persons using AI to create new inventions and this ensures that the innovation remains open in the public domain and the natural person, who has been assigned or licensee reaps economic benefit through the AI-generated invention and this mechanism makes the concept of AI being granted the inventorship a possible event”[103].

Conclusion The existing patent law framework is presently adequate or not is still question for the policy maker for addressing questions of patentability concerning the current generation

of Artificial Intelligence technologies. However, it is urgency to assess and address the legal and policy challenges posed by the advanced AI systems, such as strong AI and superintelligence. A key issue in this evolving challenge is the related to legal responsibility to such independent systems and the establishment of appropriate regulatory framework and laws to ensure accountability and control on patentability of AI generated invention. A fundamental legal question arises: does an AI system possessing such capabilities and be recognized as an "inventor" under existing patent law? The resolution of this question mandatory due to advancement, as it will help the formulation of subsequent policy measures and legal framework. The question arises Should AI attain a level of superintelligence that meets or exceeds current expectations, as it raises the prospect of AI systems performing all key functions in the patent process without human intervention, identifying patentable subject matter which are available in current society, conducting prior research related to an art, drafting and filing applications as per law, and even monitoring for potential infringement by the offenders. This scenario necessitates a futuristic legislative and regulatory framework to ensure that the patent system remains effective, fair, and adaptive to meet the technological advancement.

References

1. World Intellectual Property Organization
2. "PATENT LAWS AND THEIR SERVICE FOR IP RIGHTS", (2025), available at <https://articles.manupatra.com/article-details/PATENT-LAWS-AND-THEIR-SERVICE-FOR-IP-RIGHTS> (last accessed on April 04, 2025).
3. *The Indian Patents and Designs Act, 1911*, No. 2 of 1911
4. *The Patents Act, 1970*, (Act 39 of 1970)
5. "Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS)", Marrakesh Agreement Establishing the World Trade Organization, Annex 1C, Apr. 15, 1994, 1869 U.N.T.S. 299.
6. *The Patents and Designs Act, 1856* (Act XV of 1856) (India) (repealed).
7. "PATENT LAWS AND THEIR SERVICE FOR IP RIGHTS", available at <https://articles.manupatra.com/article-details/PATENT-LAWS-AND-THEIR-SERVICE-FOR-IP-RIGHTS> (last accessed on April 05, 2025).
8. *The Indian Patents and Designs Act, 1911* (Act 2 of 1911) (India).
9. *History of Patent Law in India*, The Legal School (Jan. 11, 2023), available at <https://thelegalschool.in/blog/history-of-patent-law-in-india> (last accessed on April 05, 2025).
10. *Ibid.*
11. "PATENT LAWS AND THEIR SERVICE FOR IP RIGHTS", Manupatra Articles, available at <https://articles.manupatra.com/article-details/PATENT-LAWS-AND-THEIR-SERVICE-FOR-IP-RIGHTS> (last accessed on April 01, 2025).
12. *Ibid.*
13. "PATENT LAWS AND THEIR SERVICE FOR IP RIGHTS", Manupatra Articles, available at <https://articles.manupatra.com/article-details/PATENT-LAWS-AND-THEIR-SERVICE-FOR-IP-RIGHTS> (last accessed on April 01, 2025).
14. "History of Indian Patent System", Intellectual Property India (Aug. 21, 2021, 2:20 PM), available at <https://ipindia.gov.in/history-of-indian-patent-system.htm> (last accessed on April 28, 2025).
15. *Ibid.*
16. "History of Indian Patent System", Intellectual Property India (Aug. 21, 2021, 2:20 PM), available at <https://ipindia.gov.in/history-of-indian-patent-system.htm> (last accessed on April 28, 2025).
17. *Ibid.*
18. "History of Indian Patent System", Intellectual Property India (Aug. 21, 2021, 2:20 PM), available at <https://ipindia.gov.in/history-of-indian-patent-system.htm> (last accessed on April 28, 2025).
19. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), Ch. I
20. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), s. 1
21. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), s. 2
22. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), Ch. II
23. *The Patents Act, 1970*, (Act 39 of 1970), s. 3
24. *The Patents Act, 1970*, (Act 39 of 1970), s. 4
25. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), Ch. III
26. *The Patents Act, 1970*, (Act 39 of 1970), s. 6
27. *The Patents Act, 1970*, (Act 39 of 1970), s. 11
28. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), Ch. IV
29. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), s. 25
30. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), s. 28
31. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), Ch. VI
32. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), s. 29
33. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), s. 34
34. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), Ch. VII
35. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), s. 35
36. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), s. 42
37. *The Patents Act, 1970* (Act 39 of 1970), Ch. VIII

38. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 43
39. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 53
40. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. IX
41. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 54
42. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 56
43. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. X
44. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 57
45. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 59
46. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XI
47. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 60
48. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 63
49. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XII
50. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 63
51. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 64
52. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XIII
53. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 67
54. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 72
55. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XIV
56. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 73
57. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 76
58. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XV
59. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 77
60. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 81
61. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XVI
62. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 82
63. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 94
64. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XVII
65. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 99
66. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 103
67. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XVIII
68. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 104
69. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 114
70. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XIX
71. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 118
72. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 124
73. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, Ch. XX
74. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 125
75. *The Patents Act, 1970 (Act 39 of 1970)*, s. 162
76. "Philip C. Jackson, *Introduction to Artificial Intelligence*, 3rd edn., Dover Publications, Inc., 1985".
77. Encyclopaedia Britannica, available at <https://www.britannica.com/technology/artificial-intelligence> (last visited on 03 April 2025).
78. "National Defence Authorization Act, 2019 (US)", s. 238(g)."
79. "MPDV, available at <https://www.mpdv.com/en/industry-4-0/artificial-intelligence-manufacturing/whats-ai> (last visited on 28 April 2025)"
80. "WIPO, available at: https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_698.pdf. Last visited date 23 January 2025"
81. "Russ Pearlman, "Recognizing Artificial Intelligence (AI) as Authors and Inventors under US Intellectual Property Law", RJLT, 2018."
82. "Ziyad Saleh, *Artificial Intelligence Definition, Ethics and Standards*, ResearchGate, 2019."
83. "V.K. Ahuja, *Artificial Intelligence And Copyright: Issues And Challenges*, 2020, ILI Law Review, 2020."
84. World Intellectual Property Organization, "Patents," available at: <https://www.wipo.int/en/web/patents> (last visited April 4, 2025).
85. "Artificial Intelligence and Patent Law: Analyzing Patentability of AI-Generated Works," (2022) 63 PULR, available at: <https://pulr.puchd.ac.in/index.php/pulr/article/download/285/55/1108> (last visited April 4, 2025).
86. "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Patents," (2024) 11(2) *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities* 63–72, available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381829157_The_Impact_of_Artificial_Intelligence_on_Patents (last visited May 4, 2025).
87. "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Patents," (2024) 11(2) *International Journal of Recent Research in Social Sciences and Humanities* 63–72, available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381829157_The_Impact_of_Artificial_Intelligence_on_Patents (last visited May 4, 2025).
88. *The Patents Act, 1970*, s. 6
89. *The Patents Act, 1970*, s. 2(1)(y)
90. V.B. Mohammed Ibrahim v. Alfred Schafranek, AIR 1960 Mys 173
91. [1]Amartya Saha, "Patentability of Artificial Intelligence: Understanding the Realm of Artificial Intelligence (AI)," (2020) 2(1) *International Journal of Integrated Law*

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- Review 1–8, available at: <https://www.ijilr.org/wp-content/uploads/Patentability-of-Artificial-Intelligence-An-Indian-Perspective.pdf> (last visited April 8, 2025).
92. *Supra* No. 5
93. Amartya Saha, "Patentability of Artificial Intelligence: Understanding the Realm of Artificial Intelligence (AI)," (2020) 2(1) *International Journal of Integrated Law Review* 1–8, available at: <https://www.ijilr.org/wp-content/uploads/Patentability-of-Artificial-Intelligence-An-Indian-Perspective.pdf> (last visited April 8, 2025).
94. Amartya Saha, "Patentability of Artificial Intelligence: Understanding the Realm of Artificial Intelligence (AI)," (2020) 2(1) *International Journal of Integrated Law Review* 1–8, available at: <https://www.ijilr.org/wp-content/uploads/Patentability-of-Artificial-Intelligence-An-Indian-Perspective.pdf> (last visited April 8, 2025).
95. Amartya Saha, "Patentability of Artificial Intelligence: Understanding the Realm of Artificial Intelligence (AI)," (2020) 2(1) *International Journal of Integrated Law Review* 1–8, available at: <https://www.ijilr.org/wp-content/uploads/Patentability-of-Artificial-Intelligence-An-Indian-Perspective.pdf> (last visited April 8, 2025).
96. *Ibid*
97. *Ibid*
98. *Thaler v. Vidal*, 43 F.4th 1207 (Fed. Cir. 2022)
99. *Goldstein v. California*, 412 U.S. 546 (1973)
100. *Goldstein v. California*, 412 U.S. 546 (1973)
101. *Goldstein v. California*, 412 U.S. 546 (1973)
102. *Burroughs Wellcome Co. v. Barr Labs., Inc.*, 40 F.3d 1223
103. "Artificial Intelligence and Patent Law: Analyzing Patentability of AI-Generated Works," (2022) 63 *PULR*, available at: <https://pulr.puchd.ac.in/index.php/pulr/article/download/285/55/1108> (last visited April 4, 2025).